

Chemical Modification of Selected Root and Tuber Starches as Thickening and Stabilizing Agents in Double-Strength Fruit Juice

Ifediba, Donald I.^{1*}Owuamanam, Clifford I.²and Obichili, Irene O.³

1. Department of Agricultural Technology, Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu, Nigeria 2. Department of Food Science and Technology, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Nigeria 3. Department of Home and Rural Economics, Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu, Nigeria.

*Email of the Corresponding author: ifedibad@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The food application of native and chemically modified starches from white guinea yam (*Discorea rotundata*) and sweet potato (*Ipoema batatas*) tubers as substitute for cereal starches was studied. Yam tuber and potato root were processed to extract their native starches. The native starch were chemically modified by acid hydrolysis using dilute hydrochloric acid, acetylated with acetic anhydride and oxidized with sodium hypochlorite respectively. The starch samples were analyzed for rheological and functional properties, using commercial corn starch as a control. The starch samples were further incorporated into single strength orange juice as thickening and stabilizing agent. Triplicate values of data obtained were analyzed using SPSS Version 22 and means were compared for significant difference at 95% confidence level using Turkey's LSD Test. Results showed that modified yam and potato starches recorded high values in all the rheological and functional parameters considered. Sensory evaluation scores of the orange fruit juice show that some yam and potato starches were superior to the commercial corn starch in all the attributes considered. It follows that imported cereal starch can be conveniently substituted with root and tuber starches to meet the industrial demand of starch in developing economies.

Keywords: Polymers; Starches; Modification, Application; Properties, Tubers

INTRODUCTION

Starch is second to cellulose as the most abundant organic compound in nature. It is a naturally occurring biodegradable, cheap, renewable, and abundantly available polysaccharide in plants. It is essentially composed of two polyglucans namely amylose (AM) and amylopectin (AP). Amylopectin is the major component in most starches.

Starch is currently enjoying increased attention owing to its usefulness in different food products where it contributes greatly to the textural properties of food stuff. It is widely used in food and industrial applications as a thickener, colloidal stabilizer, gelling agent, bulking agent, water retention agent, edible coatings and numerous non-food uses.

Native starch is a white powder with bland taste and flavor, and is insoluble in cold water. In a typical manufacturing process that uses a combination of wet purification techniques, drying and milling, starch is separated from other constituents such as fibers, proteins, sugars and salts to obtain native starch with a purity of about 98 to 99.5% (Korma et al., 2016). Native starches have been widely used in some industries, however their sub-optimal properties such as insolubility in cold water, low shear stress resistance, loss of viscosity and thickening power after cooking, thermal degradation, high tendency towards retro-gradation and syneresis, among other deficiencies, have greatly limited their industrial applications (Kavlani et al., 2012). Native starches are often modified to stabilize starch granules during processing in order to develop specific properties such as solubility, texture, adhesion, and heat tolerance, so as to be suitable for industrial purposes (Veira and Sarmiento, 2008; Yan and Zhengbiao, 2010).

Therefore, to meet the technological requirements of today, variety of modification methods have been designed in order to address the shortcomings of the native starch. Generally, there are four broad classifications of starch modifications: chemical, physical, enzymatic, and genetic. Chemical modification as will be employed in this research involves the introduction of functional groups into the starch molecules, resulting in markedly altered physicochemical properties. It is generally achieved through derivatization (etherification, esterification, cross-linking and grafting of starch); decomposition or degradation (acid or enzymatic hydrolysis, oxidation of starch and dual modification).

Starchy roots and tubers are plants which store edible starch material in subterranean stems, roots, rhizomes, corms, and tubers and are originated from diversified botanical sources. They include potatoes, cassava, sweet potatoes, yams, and aroids belonging to different botanical families but are grouped

together as underground food. In most developing countries, particularly Nigeria, demands for industrial purpose starches are often met through imports rather than local supply, despite abundance of tropical root and tuber crops like yam and sweet potato. Nevertheless, cereal crops such as wheat, rye, maize continue to dominate global starch production, which are imported at a considerably prohibitive cost. Yet tuber starches do not contain gluten which could lead to health challenges do to gluten intolerance. Furthermore, it is estimated that an average of 30% loss occurs during storage of roots and tubers in the humid tropics, arising from harsh climate conditions, inadequate facilities for fresh food preservation, and limited processing capacity. This monumental loss can be mitigated by converting substantial quantities of the produce to native and modified starches for sundry use, thus encouraging value addition.

Perhaps inadequate information on innate properties of native and modified starches from tropical root and tuber crops is responsible for the reliance on imported brands, with high foreign exchange demands. Chemical modification by acetylation, acid degradation and oxidation could retune the properties of these local starches to meet the demands of the local food industry.

Native starch from white Guinea yam (*Discorea rotundata*) and sweet potato (*Ipoema batatas*) will be chemically modified using hydrochloric acid (acid hydrolysis), acetic anhydride (acetylation) and sodium hypochlorite (oxidation). The starch samples will be further used as thickening and stabilizing agents in double strength orange fruit juice. The native and modified starches will be subjected to Functional, Rheological property tests, while the fruit juice will be subjected Sensory evaluation..

METHODOLOGY

Sourcing of Raw Material

Fresh tubers of white Guinea yam (*Discorea rotundata*) and sweet potato (*Ipoema batatas*) were procured from growers at Otuocha Agricultural Belt, Anambra East Local Government Area, Anambra State and authenticated at National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI) Extension Igbariam, Anambra State State, Nigeria.

Sample Production

Extraction of yam starch

Yam starch was extracted according to the method of Jiang et al. (2013).

Extraction of native yam starch

Yam starch was extracted according to the method of Jiang et al. (2013). The yam tuber was washed, hand-peeled, reduced to thin slices submerged in sodium metabisulphite (0.25%). The chips were wet-milled in a laboratory food blender using distilled water three times the volume of the yam slices. The slurry was consecutively sieved through 100 mesh (BSS) screens using distilled water until filtrate was free from impurities. The filtrate was left to settle for 1h and the supernatant was decanted. The sediment was consecutively re-suspended in distilled water (three times the sediment volume), centrifuged and passed through 100 mesh sieve until the supernatant became transparent. The colored top layer was manually scrapped and the white layer was re-suspended in distilled water and centrifuged as before, until the top starch layer is devoid of coloration. The firm, dense and snow-white paste was dried in an air oven at 40°C for 24h. The dried paste was milled to pass through 150µm sieve, packed in air tight container and stored under dry conditions at room temperature until use.

Extraction of native sweet potato starch

Potato starch was extracted using the method of Ammar (2018). The potato tubers were washed, peeled and reduced to shreds submerged in sodium metabisulphite (0.25%). The shredded mass was wet-milled in a laboratory blender using distilled water three times the volume of the potato shreds. The slurry was consecutively sieved through 200 mesh (BSS) sieve using distilled water until filtrate was free from impurities. The filtrate was left to settle for 1 h. The supernatant was decanted and the sediment was consecutively re-suspended in distilled water (three times the sediment volume), centrifuged and passed through 100 mesh (BSS) sieve until the supernatant became transparent. The colored top layer was manually scrapped and the white layer re-suspended in distilled water and centrifuged as before, until the top starch layer was devoid of coloration. The firm, dense and snow-white paste was dried in an air oven at 40°C for 24h. The dried paste was milled to pass through 150µm sieve, packed in air tight container and stored under dry conditions at room temperature until use.

Modification of native starches by Acid hydrolysis

The method described by Sandhu et al. (2007) for preparation of acid-modified starch was slightly modified. 500g (dry basis) of each of the native starches obtained from yam and potato were respectively dispersed in 1L 6% HCL solution. The reaction was left to stand for 10h in a water bath at 40°C without stirring. The suspension was neutralized with 10% (w/v) NaOH solution and the starch slurry was washed three times with twofold volume of deionized water and dried in a convection oven at 40°C for 24h. It was milled and passed through a 125 µm mesh sieve, packed in air tight container and stored under dry conditions at room temperature until use.

Modification of native starches by Acetylation

The method described by Mbougung et al. (2012) was slightly modified. 100g (dry basis) of each of the native starches obtained from yam and potato were respectively dispersed in 225 ml of distilled water and was continuously stirred to dissolution. The pH of the slurry was adjusted to 8.0 with 0.5M NaOH. Acetic anhydride (8g) was added drop wise to the stirred slurry, while maintaining the pH within the range of 8.0 - 8.5 using the NaOH solution. The reaction continued for 60min before adjusting to pH4.5 with dilute HCL (0.2M). After sedimentation, the starch was washed free of acid, thrice with threefold of distilled water and once with 95% ethanol, and oven dried at 40°C for 24h. It was milled and passed through a 125 µm mesh sieve, packed in an air tight container and stored under dry conditions at room temperature until use.

Modification of native starch by Oxidation

The method of Wojeicchowksi et al. (2017) was slightly modified. A 35% (w/w) starch suspension from yam and potato native starches were respectively prepared and the pH adjusted to 9.5 with 0.1M NaOH solution. Standardized sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution (2g active chlorine/100g starch) was slowly added, while the pH of the suspension was kept at 9.5. After complete addition of NaOCl the suspension was maintained at the same pH for 60 min. The pH was adjusted to 7.0 with dilute HCL (0.1M). The modified starch was recovered by filtration and washed until complete removal of the ClO⁻ ions. The starch was oven dried at 40°C for 24h, milled and passed through a 125 µm mesh sieve, packed in an air tight container and stored under dry conditions at room temperature until use.

ANALYSIS OF STARCH SAMPLES

Water absorption capacity (WAC): This was determined according to the method of Onwuka (2005).

Water binding capacity: The water binding capacity of the samples was determined according to the method described by Bustillos-Rodriguez et al. (2018).

Swelling power (SP): The method of Santacruz et al. (2003) was used.

Viscosity: Apparent viscosity was determined on emulsion of 3g of starch in 25g of distilled water using digital viscometer with a mean value taken from triplicate runs.

Density: Loose and Tapped Bulk density was determined according to the method of Onwuka (2005).

Void Ratio: Void ratio was calculated as ratio of Void volume to Total volume as obtained from Loose and Tapped density procedure.

Gelatinization temperature: Gelatinization temperature was determined according to the method of Onwuka (2005) will be used.

Sensory Test: Twenty man panel drawn from the Polytechnic community was used and samples were evaluated on a 9-point Hedonic scale.

Experimental design and Statistical analysis

The experimental design for the study is a 2 x3 factor experiment (with triple replication), comprising of two tropical tuber crops (yam and sweet potato) and three treatments (acid hydrolysis, oxidation and acetylation). The data was analyzed using IB M SPSS Version 22 and significant difference in means of triplicate values was determined using Turkey’s LSD test at 95% confidence level.

RESULTS

Table 1 Rheological properties of starch samples

SAMPLES	PARAMETER			
	Loose bulk density (g/mi)	Tapped bulk density (g/mi)	Void ratio	Apparent viscosity Pa.S
APS	0.585 ^e	0.848 ^c	0.449 ^b	315.15 ^f
AYS	0.717 ^b	0.901 ^a	0.263 ^f	479.05 ^a
HPS	0.668 ^c	0.841 ^c	0.261 ^f	422.15 ^c
HYS	0.760 ^a	0.868 ^b	0.148 ^h	363.80 ^d
NPS	0.646 ^d	0.891 ^a	0.357 ^c	470.75 ^a
NYS	0.695 ^b	0.691 ^e	0.286 ^e	330.65 ^e
CCS	0.546 ^f	0.737 ^d	0.346 ^d	240.40 ^g
OPS	0.595 ^e	0.872 ^b	0.461 ^a	329.15 ^e
OYS	0.748 ^a	0.887 ^b	0.186 ^g	467.95 ^{ab}

Means of triplicate samples of starches with different superscripts within a column are significantly (p<0.05) different. APS acetylated potato starch, AYS acetylated yam starch, HPS hydrolyzed

potato starch, HYS hydrolyzed yam starch, NPS native potato starch, NYS native yam starch, CCS commercial corn starch, OPS oxidized potato starch, OYS oxidized yam starch.

Table 2 Functional properties of starch samples

PARAMETERS	SAMPLES								
	APS	AYS	HPS	HYS	NPS	NYS	CCS	OPS	OYS
Water absorption capacity (x IPS density)	2.00 ^{ab}	1.40	2.05 ^b	1.85 ^c	1.70 ^d	2.10 ^b	3.25 ^a	1.80 ^c	1.45 ^e
Water binding capacity (x 10 ²)	2.71 ^c	36 ^h	1.60 ^g	2.63 ^{cd}	1.81 ^f	3.60 ^a	3.00 ^b	1.94 ^e	2.08 ^d
Swelling power: 60°C	9.63 ^a	7.63 ^b	4.98 ^f	5.57 ^c	2.67 ^h	5.15 ^e	5.66 ^c	4.34 ^g	5.45 ^d
70°C	12.26 ^a	3.67 ^e	1.77 ^h	2.13 ^g	8.45 ^b	3.68 ^e	6.15 ^d	6.67 ^c	2.84 ^f
80°C	21.41 ^a	9.92 ^e	2.41 ^h	1.59 ⁱ	15.57 ^c	8.34 ^g	9.41 ^f	18.84 ^b	14.77 ^d
Gelatinization temperature	75 ^b	62 ^{cd}	85 ^a	81 ^a	63 ^{cd}	77 ^b	66 ^c	59 ^d	72 ^{ab}

Means of triplicate samples of starches with different superscripts within a row are significantly (p<0.05) different. APS, AYS, HPS, HYS, NPS, NYS, CCS, OPS, OYS are as in Table 1.

Table 3 Sensory evaluation of orange juice thickened with varietal starch samples

SAMPLES	ATTRIBUTES			Overall acceptability
	Color	Flavor	Mouth feel	
APSTOJ	5.13 ^f	6.13 ^d	5.37 ^d	5.50 ^{bc}
AYSTOJ	7.50 ^a	6.75 ^b	6.63 ^a	6.75 ^a
HPSTOJ	6.63 ^b	7.12 ^a	6.75 ^a	6.73 ^a
HYSTOJ	6.62 ^b	6.38 ^c	6.62 ^a	6.25 ^{ab}
NPSTOJ	6.63 ^b	6.00 ^d	6.50 ^b	5.88 ^{bc}
NYSTOJ	6.25 ^d	6.38 ^c	6.25 ^b	6.13 ^{ab}
CCSTOJ	5.63 ^e	6.00 ^d	5.75 ^c	5.25 ^c
OPSTOJ	6.38 ^c	7.00 ^a	6.63 ^a	6.50 ^a
OYSTOJ	6.50 ^c	5.00 ^e	6.37 ^b	5.50 ^c

Means of triplicate samples of starches with different superscripts within a column are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different APSTOJ acetylated potato starch thickened orange juice, AYSTOJ acetylated yam starch thickened orange juice, HPSTOJ hydrolyzed potato starch thickened orange juice, HYSTOJ hydrolyzed yam starch thickened orange juice, NPSTOJ native potato starch thickened orange juice, NYSTOJ native yam starch thickened orange juice, CCSTOJ commercial corn starch thickened orange juice, OPSTOJ oxidized potato starch thickened orange juice, OYSTOJ oxidized yam starch thickened orange juice.

Discussion of Results

Rheological properties

As seen in Table 1 there was significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the loose bulk density of starch samples with HYS highest at 0.760 and CCS lowest at 0.546. There was also significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in tapped bulk density with NYS lowest at 0.691 and AYS highest at 0.901. The values closely relate with the range values of 0.613 to 0.743 reported for trifoliate yam landraces by Ezeocha and Okafor (2016). The void ratio of starch samples significantly differed from 0.148 of HYS to 0.461 of OPS. Void ratio is an indication of porosity of the starch particles which inversely relates to the difference between the loose and tapped volumes of a starch sample. Starch porosity is highly important in rheology because it directly impacts the water absorption capacity of starch granules during gelatinization, thus influencing the viscosity and texture of starch paste or gel and ultimately contributes to the characteristics of food products where starch is used as thickener or stabilizer. Higher porosity results in greater swelling power as is true for OPS compared to other samples under review. The samples significantly varied in apparent viscosity, ranging from 240.40 of CCS to 479.05 of AYS, suggesting that viscosity is interplay of porosity, solubility, gelation and dispensability of starch granules when dispersed in a liquid phase, among other factors..

Functional property

Results in Table 2 show that there was significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in water absorption capacity of starch samples with NYS having the highest value of 2.1 compared with the lowest value of 1.4 of AYS. The values for yam starch samples were however lower than the 7.0 for

Discorea rotundata flour by Tortoe and Dowuona (2017) and the 9.7 to 10.2 of trifoliolate yam (*Discorea dumetorum*) starch by Ezeocha and Okafor (2016). The higher value of the *D. rotundata* flour may be due to the contributory effect of other macromolecules present in yam flour which are eliminated during starch extraction. The values are far below the 267.4 and 154.7 of bread fruit whole and pulp flours by Adepeju et al. (2011), probably due to high presence of fiber and other polymeric components. Water absorption capacity (WAC) reflects the amount of water the starch can hold in relation to its weight (Awoyale et al., 2016). Water absorption is an indication of the integrity of starch in aqueous dispersion (Leonel, 2007). There was significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in swelling power (SP) of the starch samples ranging far between 2.84 to 14.786, with the highest value obtained at 80°C. The values correlates the 10.48 to 13.35 for yam flour varieties by Tortoe and Dowuona (2017) and earlier study by Wireko-Manu et al. (2011). The swelling power response to temperature rise is also in agreement with changes observed for taro, yam and sweet potato flours and starches by Aprianita et al. (2009). The lower values of modified starch samples may be due to granular alteration affecting pore size as well as structural damage due to treatment method. The water binding capacity (WBC) of the samples varied significantly between 60% in HPS and 260% in NYS.. The higher WBC of yam starch samples may be due to greater number of available binding sites for water in starch granules (Sandhu et al, 2007). Gelatinization temperature of starch samples significantly differed ranging from 59°C of OPS to 85°C of HPS. The values correlates with the 56.96°C to 84.67°C for taro, yam and sweet potato starches (Aprianita et al., 2009), 61.1°C to 71.1°C for starches derived from traditional Indonesian tubers and roots (Aprianita et al. 2014) and 80.00°C to 82.50°C for trifoliolate yam (Ezeocha and Okafor, 2016). Lower gelatinization temperature entails that lower energy would be required to initiate gelatinization (Hover and Ratnayake, 2005), which could be advantageous for foods containing heat labile ingredients. Gelatinization affects the digestibility and texture of starch containing foods (Ezeocha and Okafor, 2016).

Sensory evaluation

There was significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in color of orange fruit juice mixed with equal weights of starch samples as thickening and stabilizing agents. The difference in color may be attributed

to variation in the color shades of starch samples which impacted on the juice color. The comparatively deeper color of yam starches in the native and modified forms may have contributed to its color preference. Nevertheless, there was no significant difference in the color of some of the fruit juice, being that color differences of the respective starch samples are marginal. The more whitish color of CCS may have tainted the natural orange color of the juice to render it least attractive. There was significant difference in the flavor of the juice the modified potato starch containing samples being more preferred. The lowest flavor score of OYSTOJ suggests that acid hydrolysis of yam starch may trigger adverse flavor development, hence impacting negatively on flavor of the orange juice. There were significant and marginal differences in the mouth feel of some the juice, an indication that some of the starch samples had similar contribution to the texture of the orange juice. Mouth feel is a prediction of textural characteristics of colloidal dispersions which determines the suitability of an additive as thickening and stabilizing agent. It is a sensorial tool that assesses the rheological behavior of an ingredient in aqueous dispersion. There was significant and marginal difference in the overall acceptability of the samples with AYSTOJ receiving the highest score closely followed by HPSTOJ. It would appear that acetylation and hydrolysis inversely affected the overall acceptability of potato and yam starches respectively; a phenomenon that requires further scientific probe. The least overall acceptance of CCSTOJ may be due to the low viscosity, brighter color and perceivable corn flavor, thus suggesting that root and tuber starches can be conveniently substituted for cereal starch as thickening and stabilizing agent in fruit juice.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This research reveals that yam and potato starches can be readily extracted as native starch and chemically modified to enhance their rheological and functional properties. It also proved that starch from root and tuber sources can replace cereal starch, particularly the popular commercial corn starch, as thickening and stabilizing agents in fruit juice. A further study is recommended to address limitations of diverse modification methods in order to optimize the production of tropical root and tuber starches for commercial and industrial purposes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Tertiary Education Fund (TETFund) Nigeria for their funding through the Institutional Based Research (IBR) intervention, and to the management of Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu, Nigeria for endorsing our application for sponsorship.

REFERENCES

- Adepeju, A.B., Gbadamosi, S.O., Adeniran, A.H., and Omobuwaju, T.O. (2011). Functional and pasting characteristics of breadfruit (*Artocarpus altilis*) flours. *African Journal of Food Science*, 5(9): 529 – 535.
- Aprianita, A., Vasiljevic, T., Banikova, A. , and Kasepis, S. (2014). Physicochemical properties of flours and starches derived from traditional Indonesian tubers and roots. *Journal of Food Science Technology*, 5(12): 3669 – 3679.
- Aprianita, A., Purwandari, U., Watson, B., and Vasijevic, T. (2009). Physicochemical properties of flours and starches from selected commercial tubers available in Australia. *International Food Research Journal*, 16: 507 – 520.
- Awoyale, W., Maziya-Dixon, B., Sanni, L.O., and Shitu, T.A. (2016). Effect of water yam (*Discorea alata*) flour fortified distiller's spent grain on nutritional, chemical and functional properties. *Food Science and Nutrition*, 4: 24 – 33.
- Ammar A. (2018). Extraction and optimization of potato starch and its application as a stabilizer in yogurt manufacturing. *Foods*, 7(2): 14 DOI: 103390/foods 7020014 License. CC BY 4.0.
- Bustillos-Rodriguez, J.C., Tirado-gallegos, J.M., Ordonez-gargia, M. and Zamudio-Flores, P.B. (2018). Physicochemical, thermal and rheological properties of three native corn starch. *Food Science and Technology*, 39(1):1-11.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/fst.28117>.
- Ezeocha, C.V. and Okafor, J.C. (2016). Evaluation of the chemical, functional and pasting properties of starch from trifoliolate yam (*Discorea dumetorum*) landraces. *European Journal of Advanced Research in Biological and Life Sciences*, 4(2): 53 – 62.
- Hoover, R., and Ratnayake, W.S. (2005). Determination of total amylose content of starch. In: Wrolstad RE, Acree TE, Deckert EA et al., editors. *Handbook of food analytical chemistry, water, proteins, enzymes, lipids, and carbohydrates*. New Jersey: Wiley, pp 689 – 693.
- Jiang, Q., Gao, W., Shi, V., Li, X., Wang, H., Huang, L. and Xiao, P. (2013). Physicochemical properties and in vitrodigestion of starches from different *Discorea* plants. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 32: 432-439.

- Kavlani, N., Sharma, V. and Singh, L. (2012). Various techniques for the modification of starch and the application of its derivatives. *International Journal of Pharmacy*, 3(5): 25-40.
- Korma, S.A., Alahmed, K., Niazi, S., Ammar, A., Zaaboul, F. and Zhang, T. (2016). Chemically modified starch and utilization in food stuffs. *International Journal of Nutrition and Food Science*, 5(4): 264 – 272.
- Leonel, M., Sarmiento, S.B.S. and Cereda, M.P. (2009). New starches for the food industry. *Curcuma Longa and Curcuma Zedoaria. Carbohydrate Polymers*, 54: 385 – 388.
- Mbougueng, P.D., Tenin, D., Scher, J. and Tchiegang, C. (2012). Influence of acetylation on physicochemical, functional and thermal properties of potato and cassava starches. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 108: 320-326.
- Onwuka, G.I., (2005). Food analysis and instrumentation theory and practical. Naphthali prints, a division of H.G Support Nig Ltd. Published in Surulere, Lagos, Nigeria, pp 122-125.
- Sandhu, K.S., Singh, N. and Lim, S.T. (2007). A comparison of native and acid thinned normal and waxy corn starches: physicochemical, thermal, morphological and pasting properties. *Lebensmittelswissenschaft Technology*, 40(9): 1527-1536.
- Santacruz, S., Rualesa, J. and Eliasson, A.C. (2003). Three under-utilized sources of starch from the Andean region in Ecuador. Part II. Rheological characterization. *Carbonhydrate Polymers*, 51: 85-92. doi:10.1016/s0144-8617 (02)00140-6.
- Tortoe, C. and Dowuona, S. (2017). Examining the physicochemical, functional and rheological properties of flours of farmers, 7 key yam (*Discorea* spp.) varieties in Ghana to enhance yam production. Council for Science and Industrial Research – Food Research Institute, Box M20 Accra Ghana.
- Wireko-Manu, F.D., Ellis, W.O., Oduro, J., Asiedu, R., and Maziya-Dixon, B. (2011). Physicochemical and pasting characteristics of water yam (*D. alata*) in comparison with Pona (*D. rotundata*) from Ghana. *European Journal of Food Research Revision*, 1: 149 – 158.
- Veira, F.C. and Sarmiento, S.B. (2008). Heat-moisture treatment and enzymatic digestibility of Peruvian carrot, sweet potato and ginger starches. *Starch/Starke*, 60: 223-238.
- Wojeicchowski, J.P., Siqueira, G.L., Lacerda, L.G., Schnitzler, E. and Demiate, I.M.C. (2017). Physicochemical, structural and thermal properties of oxidized, acetylated and dual-modified common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*L.) starch. *Food Science and Technology*, Campinas, 38(12): 318-327.
- Yan, H. and Zhengbiao, G.U. (2010). Morphology of modified starches prepared by different methods. *Food Research International*, 43 (3): 767-772.